

Impact of GST on Indian Businesses: Assessment and Future Prospects

Asst. Prof. Manasi Mandar Datar

Shri Shahu Mandir Mahavidyalaya, Parvati, Pune.

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Abstract:

This research paper studies the role and effects of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) on the Indian economy. GST was introduced on 1 July 2017. It replaced many indirect taxes that were earlier charged by the central and state governments. The main aim of GST was to make the tax system simpler and help in economic growth. The paper also discusses the problems faced during the early stage of GST implementation and studies its long-term impact on India's economy. The study shows that GST has helped improve tax compliance, brought many businesses from the informal sector into the formal sector, and increased government revenue. Although some sectors faced short-term difficulties after GST was introduced, the overall impact on the Indian economy has been positive. GST has helped create a more unified and integrated tax system in India.

Keywords: GST, Economic growth, Tax, Gross domestic product, GST 2.0, Indian Business, Tax Reform, MSMEs, Formalization, Supply Chain Efficiency.

Introduction:

GST is known as the Goods and Services Tax. It is an indirect tax that has replaced many other indirect taxes in India such as excise duty, VAT, service tax, etc. The Goods and Services Tax Act was passed in Parliament on 29 March 2017 and came into effect on 1 July 2017. GST is a complete, multi-stage, destination-based tax that is charged on every value addition in the supply of goods and services.[1]

GST has helped increase tax collections and has expanded the tax base[2]. The unified tax system has improved tax compliance and has brought many previously unregistered businesses into the tax system. This has helped the government collect more revenue.

GST has also supported economic growth by encouraging investment, reducing production costs, and improving the ease of doing business in India. In the long run, GST is expected to have a positive impact on India's GDP.

In the short term, the introduction of GST caused some disruptions and uncertainties. This led to temporary changes in the prices of goods and services. However, over time, GST has helped bring better price stability and reduce inflation pressure.

GST has also made the tax filing process simpler, making it easier for businesses to follow tax rules. The single tax system has reduced the compliance burden, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

Although GST has mostly had a positive impact on the economy, some sectors faced temporary difficulties during the transition period.[3]

Objectives of the study: 1. To explore the impact of GST on Indian economy.

2. To examine the impact of GST on Indian business

Research Methodology:

The research methodology used in this study is qualitative. The researcher has used secondary data from different sources such as academic journals, databases, and reliable websites. The data is collected through a systematic review and analysis of existing literature.

IMPACT OF GST ON MICRO, SMALL, AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (MSMES):

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are very important for the Indian economy. They help in creating jobs, increasing exports, and supporting development in different regions of the country. Because of this, the impact of **GST** on MSMEs has been widely discussed.

GST was introduced to create equal opportunities for businesses and to bring MSMEs into the formal economy. However, at the same time, many MSMEs faced challenges such as following tax rules and managing cash flow after the introduction of GST.

Structural Changes in MSME Operations Post GST:

Before GST, many MSMEs worked in the informal or semi-formal sector. Many small manufacturers and traders were either not part of the tax system or they followed state taxes like VAT only sometimes. GST changed this system by introducing invoice-based taxation and digital reporting across the country.

After the introduction of GST, MSMEs were required to:

- Register on the GST portal
- Issue proper GST invoices
- File regular tax returns
- Maintain digital records of their transactions

These changes made MSME operations more organized. Earlier, many businesses worked mainly with cash and personal relationships. After GST, they had to follow proper documentation and tax compliance.

Working Capital Stress and Input Tax Credit (ITC) Delays:

Under GST, tax liability arises at the time of invoice issuance rather than receipt of payment. This means that MSMEs are required to pay GST on sales even if customers delay payment. Furthermore, ITC can only be claimed if 1) The supplier has uploaded the invoice 2) The supplier has filed returns 3) The tax has been deposited with the government. Any delay or non-compliance by suppliers results in ITC blockage for the MSME buyer. This disrupts cash flows and increases reliance on short-term borrowing.

Impact on Small Manufacturers :

While large manufacturers benefitted immediately, small manufacturers faced adjustment costs. Compliance requirements, e-invoicing thresholds, and working capital pressures disproportionately affected smaller units. Over time, however, compliant small manufacturers gained access to larger markets and formal financing, gradually improving competitiveness.

GST AND THE MANUFACTURING SECTOR :

The manufacturing sector has been one of the primary beneficiaries of GST due to the elimination of cascading taxes and seamless credit flow across goods and services. Reduction in Cascading Effects Before GST, manufacturers paid excise duty on production and VAT on sales, with limited cross credit availability. Taxes embedded in input inflated production costs and distorted pricing decisions. GST eliminated these cascading effects by allowing full credit across the value chain. For manufacturers, this resulted in 1) Lower effective tax incidence 2) Improved cost transparency 3) Rationalized pricing structures which means pricing system becomes **clear and balanced**, without unnecessary or extra taxes or charges. This helps in **keeping prices more stable and transparent** for both businesses and consumers.

GST AND THE SERVICES SECTOR:

Under GST, services are taxed based on the place of supply. Because of this change, service providers had to adjust their invoicing, registration, and tax compliance processes. Large service companies that operate across India benefited from the uniform tax system. However, smaller service providers faced difficulties in following tax rules in multiple states. Small service providers faced difficulties related to: 1) Multiple registrations 2) Place-of-supply determination.

IMPACT OF GST ON E-COMMERCE AND DIGITAL BUSINESSES:

The e-commerce and digital services sector has emerged as one of the fastest-growing segments of the Indian economy. GST has played an important role in operational, compliance of digital businesses.[4]

GST Framework for E-Commerce Operators Under GST, e-commerce operators (ECOs) are subject to special compliance provisions, including mandatory registration irrespective of turnover and the requirement to collect Tax Collected at Source (TCS). This framework was designed to improve traceability of online transactions and prevent tax leakage in the digital economy.

GST has contributed positively to India's ease of doing business by simplifying indirect taxation and improving logistics efficiency. However, compliance intensity remains a concern, particularly for MSMEs.

- Positive Business Outcomes
 1. Reduced tax cascading
 2. Improved logistics efficiency
 3. Unified national market ● Enhanced tax transparency
- Persistent Challenges
 1. High compliance frequency
 2. Working capital blockage
 3. Dependence on digital infrastructure
 4. Frequent regulatory updates

Conclusion:

GST has significantly reduced the cascading effect of indirect taxes, which was a major drawback in the pre-GST regime. The seamless flow of input tax credit across goods and services has lowered embedded tax costs and improved pricing transparency.

GST has changed the supply chain and logistics system in India.[5] The removal of interstate tax barriers and having similar tax rates across the country have helped businesses improve their operations. It has encouraged companies to reduce the number of warehouses, decreased transport delays, and lowered logistics costs. These improvements have especially helped sectors like manufacturing, FMCG, pharmaceuticals, and organized retail.

Finally, the move toward **GST 2.0** effective September 22, 2025, is a major overhaul simplifying India's tax system into a two-rate structure (5% and 18%) with 40% for sin/luxury goods. Key reforms include tax cuts on essential items, construction materials (cement 28% to 18%), and vehicles aiming to boost consumption, reduce inflation, and simplify MSME compliance, shows that the government and institutions have learned from the earlier GST system and are improving it. Changes like simpler tax rates, better use of technology to check tax compliance, and the creation of the **GST Appellate Tribunal** show that the system is moving from basic setup to improvement. This new phase aims to balance the goal of increasing government revenue while also making it easier for businesses to operate.

However, the study also shows that GST compliance creates more pressure on MSMEs. They have to file taxes frequently, depend on digital systems, and sometimes face delays in getting input tax credit. This creates working capital problems for small businesses. Although becoming part of the formal system can help them get loans in the future, many MSMEs still face short-term cash flow difficulties. Goods and Services Tax (GST) has created a “One Nation, One Tax” market in India. It has given relief to producers and consumers by allowing input tax credit and by replacing many different taxes with one single tax system.

Proper implementation of GST helps both the Central and State governments increase their revenue. It improves tax compliance and also increases the tax base. GST has had a positive impact on many sectors of the economy.

However, the successful implementation of GST requires the joint efforts of all stakeholders such as the Central Government, State Governments, trade, and industry.

The GST system is mostly electronic. Tax filing, tax refunds, tax returns, and tax payments are done through the GST network (GSTN). This reduces human involvement, which helps in reducing corruption and tax evasion.

The system also checks business transactions through proper credit and return processing, which reduces the chances of black money generation and encourages better use of capital. Therefore, it is important for the government to provide training and education about GST, as it is the need of the hour.

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